

The Effect Of Accounting Disclosure For Sustainable Development On The Quality Of Financial Report And The Extent Of Its Reflection On The Company Value

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Abstract

Many accounting and financial studies have emphasized the importance of accounting disclosure in general and its link to achieving the values of abuse, transparency and credibility, and its contribution to achieving social responsibility, as indicated and noted by many studies on the link of accounting disclosure about the environmental dimensions or the dimension of human resources in creating a good impression about the company, whether in the company. Clients or stakeholders, and accordingly the study aimed to identify the impact of accounting disclosure on sustainable development on the quality of financial reports and the extent of this reflection on the value of the company order to achieve the objective of the study, the analytical, inductive and deductive approach was used by reviewing previous studies and researches. The study sample was determined by the financial reports of Almarai for the last five years.

The values of goodwill, the market value of the company and the net profit were extracted as indicators of the value of the company as well as to identify the extent of the existence of financial and environmental sustainability reports and reports. Social responsibility and sustainable development, which was noticed the company's interest in including it in the reports in the last five years, and a scale for the quality of financial reports was prepared that included five dimensions (relevance, transparency, clarity, credibility and comparability). These five dimensions were analyzed and the correlations were tested through the Pearson correlation coefficient.

The study concluded that there is a relationship. The impact between the accounting disclosure and the standards of compatibility and comparability is more than clarity transparency and credibility. The accounting disclosure on sustainable development also had an impact on the value of the company if any other investment influences that helped the growth of the company's value or its stability in some years were ignored. Therefore, we recommend raising awareness and making a special charter for the Kingdom.

Directs companies to comply with performing the disclosure accounting for sustainable development because of its positive impact on the quality of financial reports and maximizing the values of economic establishments.

Introduction

The worldwide endeavors to make and spread the principles for faultless improvement at the worldwide level proceeded through three global gatherings, the first was in Stockholm in 1972, the second in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 and the third in Johannesburg in 2002, and the latter was under the name of the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, where it characterized regions of maintainable turn of events and incorporated the monetary, social and natural fields. Every one of them incorporated a few exercises that cover with one another to accomplish practical turn of events. (Qandil, 2016)

In the event that monetary reports are the principle instrument in deciding, the quick changes in the business climate require surpassing the capacity of these reports to communicate the different elements of the estimation of the endeavor, including the degree to which organizations add to accomplishing the natural and social objectives practical developmenand since the start of the United Nations' advantage in 1992 in supportable turn of events. The organizations reacted in 1996 in the monetary reports by zeroing in on the natural and social obligation statement and the revelation of the things identified with reasonable advancement as this affected boosting benefits and subsequently a positive effect on the estimation of the organization. The assessment of organizations in the currency market stretched out from just depending on productivity and monetary situation

to incorporate the job of The organization in the public eye, the climate and the economy, which requires the organization's obligation to data exposure. (Obeid, 2020).

As indicated by the previous, the assignment of bookkeeping is not, at this point restricted to the records of approaching or active or benefits and misfortunes. Those errands went past representing ecological expenses, social duty and manageability bookkeeping. The interest in bookkeeping has moved from the idea of possession that solidified in augmenting the personal circumstance of the proprietors to the idea of the bookkeeping unit in which the proprietors are viewed as one of the partners. Subsequently, the board has zeroed in on finding some kind of harmony between the rights and commitments of the different partners. (Armouti, 2013)

Numerous investigations have likewise been worried about the effect of revelation of monetary and non-monetary data on the precision of monetary examination conjectures. The two revelation pointers are remembered for the assessment of associations as their quality, size, variety and number of correspondence channels are resolved. Most associations have affirmed that speculators can follow non-monetary data as it lessens the deviation of data in the business sectors. Monetary. (Fred, 2016)

Supportability reports give a more far reaching approach than conventional monetary reports, as they include the immediate and aberrant effect of ecological and cultural wellbeing, notwithstanding the monetary execution of the organization. Are such reports important to partners, regardless of whether banks, speculators, laborers, clients and society? There is no uncertainty that the expansion in the pattern, request and acknowledgment of proprietors The premium in these reports has added to its spread, as 93% of the 250 biggest organizations on the planet are giving these reports, and notwithstanding the significance of supportability reports and consideration regarding them, there is a variety in the structure and substance of the maintainability revelation as it is a discretionary exposure and there have been endeavors to build up a system For manageability divulgence, the most significant of which is the GRI rules, which is the most broadly acknowledged structure on the planet. (Qandil, 2016: 318)

From the abovementioned, we discover the pattern of monetary detailing considering the necessities of partners that will in general unveil manageable advancement in quest for the nature of the monetary report. A few examinations have affirmed that organizations that give great monetary data will in general be more moderate in their bookkeeping strategies and less slanted towards unscrupulous practices, for example, Profit the executives. The moderate bookkeeping strategy can be viewed as an interior drive to reveal data on social obligation and reasonable turn of events.

Numerous expert bodies around the globe have suggested the incorporation of the social and ecological report in the yearly report of the organization given. The significance of this data for the monetary interests of the gatherings related with the organization in the manner to beat shortcomings in the monetary report. (Arafa, 2016)

It is significant that the organizations' obligation to social duty and the exposure of supportable exercises amplifies the nature of bookkeeping data and improves the standing and picture of the office and its incentive in the public eye, as there is a positive connection between the reports of ecological and social duty and the monetary presentation of the office then again, which decidedly affects its position, worth and market position (Sweet and Long, 2018)

From the abovementioned, we can affirm that there is a positive effect and connection of the bookkeeping revelation that accomplishes a higher caliber of monetary reports and is portrayed by straightforwardness and validity, which underpins the situation of the organization and addresses the issues of speculators and gives them trust in the organization through the capacity to accomplish future forecasts and measure the organization's monetary exhibition, which is at last reflected in the estimation of the organization. the examination ProblemFinancial proclamations and reports address a significant device for partners to decide, and these reports don't enough communicate the estimation of the undertaking right now, henceforth the need to reveal monetary and non-monetary data, for example, manageability, corporate administration, hazard the board level, and the element's job in social and ecological issues, as such revelation of Sustainable improvement through monetary and non-monetary estimates that assess the exhibition of establishments and subsequently this impact is reflected in the estimation of the organization all in all. (El-Hajj, 2017)

The bookkeeping revelation on maintainable advancement rehearses has pulled in the consideration of global associations. The IAASB has been keen on correcting the International Standard for Assurance Services ISAE3000 with the point of giving affirmation administrations to manageability reports. The International Federation of Accountants has likewise focused on the need to remember practical advancement data for the yearly reports of organizations since this serves to Improving its presentation and its picture before speculators.

The Performance Reports Board of the Canadian Institute of Certified Public Accountants (CICA, 2010) executed an investigation on the significance of administration, social and natural obligation data for speculators. The examination affirmed that the bookkeeping exposure on manageable advancement rehearses helps speculators in assessing the exhibition of the organization and at the level of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. We find adequate premium by the controllers, as neither the introduction and exposure standard gave by

the Saudi Organization for Certified Public Accountants and Chapter Three of the Corporate Governance Regulation gave by the 2006 Law and Amended 2010 did exclude the divulgence of reasonable improvement rehearses, and no bookkeeping standard has yet been given that directs the bookkeeping treatment notwithstanding the absence of Having a model Standard C Disclosure (Meligy, 2015)

The Global Reporting Initiative, as one of the organizations that support indicators of accounting for sustainable development in economic institutions, states that the economic dimension includes sustainability with regard to the rights of stakeholders with regard to the institution and with regard to the national and global economy. This includes economic and market indicators and indirect economic impacts. The application of the accounting system for sustainable development in the economic institution requires the quality of disclosure, which is necessary for the quality of financial reports. (My boat, 2018)

From the above, the problem of the study is crystallized in what is the effect of the accounting disclosure on sustainable development on the quality of financial reports and the extent of this reflection on the value of the company?

The study questions are as follows:-

1. What is the concept of accounting disclosure and sustainable development and the relationship between them under the (GRI framework)?
2. What are the types, constituents and methods of accounting disclosure and the elements affecting it?
3. What are the criteria for the quality of financial reports, their importance and main objectives?
4. What is the accounting disclosure and its relationship to the quality of reports?
5. What is the relationship between achieving sustainable development disclosure and company value?
6. What is the relationship between accounting disclosure and the quality of investment decisions?
7. What are the determinants of disclosure of sustainable development and the benefits and advantages of sustainability reporting?

Objectives of the study.

1. Clarify the concept of accounting disclosure and sustainable development and the relationship between them under the (GRI framework).
2. Explain the types, constituents and methods of accounting disclosure and the elements affecting it.
3. Clarify the criteria for the quality, importance and basic objectives of financial reports.
4. Explain the accounting disclosure and its relationship to the quality of reports.
5. Clarify the relationship between achieving disclosure of sustainable development and the value of the company.

Explain the relationship between accounting disclosure and the quality of investment decisions.

Explain the determinants of the disclosure of sustainable development and the benefits and advantages of sustainability reports.

the importance of studying :

There are numerous examinations that affirm the effect of manageability bookkeeping exercises on the estimation of the endeavor, including the investigation (Sweet and Long, 2018) and the significance of bookkeeping divulgence on ecological exercises, including the investigation (Al-Azhar and Khaldi, 2018) and the part of supportability bookkeeping in actuating the job of establishments in accomplishing reasonable turn of events, including the investigation (Busbaeen (2014) and (Rashwan, 2018) and (Yurid, 2019) and the examination (Ghellab, 2017) introduced a proposed bookkeeping structure for the use of the bookkeeping framework for feasible improvement in the monetary organization. The examination (Al-Zamil, 2015) likewise attempted to gauge the degree of revelation of the components of corporate social duty. Saudi Industrial Share Significant in the quality and completeness of the monetary reports and their accomplishment of the objectives of speculators and the requirements of partners, which shows the effect of maintainability bookkeeping on the nature of monetary reports, which is reflected in the estimation of For the organization, straightforwardly and in a roundabout way, and subsequently this investigation will explain the relationship and feature the effect by observing the most recent 10 years of the monetary reports of the Saudi Almarai Company and contacting them to examine the relationship and effect.

The limits of the study.

Objective limits.

- Identify the impact of the accounting disclosure on sustainable development on the quality of financial reports and the quality of the company.
- Timelines: Almarai Company's financial reports from 2010 to 2019.

Terminoogy of study:

- Disclosure: It is the inclusion of the accounting reports on all the necessary information to ensure that they are not misleading to the users of the financial statements. (Armouti, 2013)
- Procedural definition: It is a measure of the extent of the comprehensiveness of accounting reports on sustainable development information in its three dimensions, which are important and necessary for users of financial statements.

Sustainability accounting:

It is a data framework worried about the two elements of estimating the natural, social and financial exhibition of the organization and providing details regarding the consequences of this estimation to guarantee the assessment of its commitments to accomplishing manageable turn of events. (Badawi and Beltagy, 2013)

Procedural definition: It is the data framework that is worried about observing and recording the natural, social and monetary exhibition of the organization and giving a report fair and square of reasonable turn of events and in this manner influences the nature of reports and the estimation of the organization.

Reasonable turn of events: It is the social, ecological and monetary measurements and their connections with partners and the supportable advancement of any organization implies the utilization of business systems and exercises that accomplish the necessities of the undertaking and its partners today while ensuring the human and characteristic assets later on. (Obaid, 2020: 13)

Procedural definition:

It is the social, monetary and natural measurements that are applied in business associations and the interest in unveiling them influences the nature of monetary reports and the estimation of the organization.

Monetary reports:

It is the principle hotspot for getting data for different gatherings, for example, current and likely financial specialists, loaning foundations, government and duty offices, and partners. It is likewise viewed as a significant pivot of rejuvenation and viability of securities exchanges, through which correspondence among the executives and any remaining invested individuals can be made through the organization through what it gives from Information to know the monetary position and the outcomes accomplished by the organization. (Abdullah, 2016: 107-108)

Procedural definition:

They are the reports that are viewed as a significant wellspring of data for financial specialists, bodies and partners and whose quality influences the presence of bookkeeping revelation writes about maintainable turn of events.

Enterprise:

It is a long-term goal that works to increase the current value of the investments of owners and shareholders, and to achieve this, the pillars and pillars that serve the enterprise's goal of maximizing value must be adopted, which is to avoid conflict of interest in light of the separation of ownership from management and the adoption of the concept of reputation management and market efficiency.

Procedural definition:

It is intended to develop the value of the enterprise as a result of the direct and indirect effect of the accounting disclosure on sustainable development and raise the quality of financial reports in it.

Chapter two

Theoretical framework and previous studies.

Previous studies.

In the study (Obaid, 2020), the study aimed to identify the effect of disclosure of sustainable development in financial reports on operational performance and its reflection on the value of companies by applying to companies whose shares are traded in the Saudi capital market for the year 2020. The study tried to present a framework through which to measure the impact of ABAD. Sustainable development on operational performance and this has a positive impact on the value of Saudi companies. The study found a positive relationship between the disclosure of sustainable development in its three dimensions in the financial reports on the operational performance of Saudi companies, as it became clear that the size of the company does not affect the disclosure of development Sustainable.

In the study (El-Gabali, 2019), the study aimed to identify the role of sustainable development accounting in increasing the reliability of financial reports, and to achieve the goal of the study, the study used the inductive, deductive, and descriptive analytical approach. Sustainable development in the Sustainability Reporting Authority, with the quantitative and descriptive financial and non-financial information it contains, while working on communicating and providing it to stakeholders is essential in assessing the value and financial performance of the company.

In the study (Sweet and Long, 2018), the study aimed to provide a framework for reviewing the activities of sustainability accounting and its impact on the value of the enterprise by applying to a sample of auditors practicing the profession. The study found a positive relationship between auditing the activities of an accounting.

The study The expressive and analytical approach was utilized by applying a poll to 150 references, and the reactions were to 120 surveys. The examination found a positive connection between the survey of maintainability bookkeeping exercises and amplifying the estimation of the venture. Consequently, the proposed system for evaluating manageability exercises attempts to boost the estimation of the organization.

In the study (Al-Hajj, 2017), the examination intended to build up a hypothetical structure for feasible improvement reports and measure the office's presentation towards monetary, social and ecological manageability objectives. To accomplish the objective of the examination, the analyst utilized the chronicled, deductive, inductive and illustrative way to deal with the contextual investigation. The investigation inferred that feasible improvement is perhaps the main reports in monetary and financial terms. The examination suggested giving a supplement as a different report from the monetary reports in the last fiscal summaries and creating execution norms for the foundations occasionally to assess the monetary and bookkeeping execution.

In the study (Arafa, 2016), the examination planned to lead an applied examination on Saudi organizations to test the connection between the bookkeeping revelation on manageable turn of events and the nature of monetary reports, notwithstanding contemplating the effect of the nature of the administration framework on the organization and to quantify the exposure on supportable turn of events. A file comprising of 46 components was developed. A total proportion of the nature of monetary reports dependent on the nature of willful advantages, bookkeeping reservation and data lopsidedness. The examination utilized them to investigate the substance by analyzing the yearly reports of 116 non-monetary organizations enrolled in the Saudi Stock Exchange in 2015, and the investigation inferred that the three proportions of the nature of the report affirm the connection with the divulgence of feasible advancement except for the bookkeeping reservation, the investigation underscored the presence of a positive effect of the effectiveness of the administration framework on the relationship with the period of revelation of supportable turn of events and the nature of the monetary report.

In the study (Farid, 2016), the examination expected to recognize the impact of the bookkeeping exposure of non-monetary data for social duty and manageability on the exactness of the expectations of monetary investigators and uncovered the intentions of associations to cling to social obligation and to accomplish the objective of the investigation, the inductive methodology and the logical methodology were utilized, and the investigation arrived at the advancement of the idea of social obligation And feasible improvement to incorporate a few viewpoints to accomplish responsibility and straightforwardness, just as there is a connection between the revelation of non-monetary data for social obligation and supportability and the precision of the forecasts of monetary experts.

In the study (Abu Zer and Al-Atoum, 2016), the study aimed to analyze sustainability indicators in a way that serves the financial and accounting sustainability of companies. To achieve this, an application study was conducted and analyzed reports of boards of directors, clarifications and attached disclosures. And liquidity and openness to market risks, and accordingly the CAPPELO approach was applied, and the study found that most companies in the Gulf countries have strategic and financial planning plans, but the level of risks varies in finding alternative sources of financing. Many industrial companies tended to generate self-income and the ability to invest resources differed, and from here a variation occurred. In its capacity for financial and accounting sustainability, the study commented that the sustainability criterion for Kuwaiti companies was the least due to the high current claims over assets and the decline in the liquidity level.

In the study (Meligy, 2015), the study aimed to examine the level of accounting disclosure (volume and quality of disclosure) on sustainable development practices with their economic, social, environmental and governance dimensions and the factors affecting on the one hand and the impact on the quality of accounting profits for companies registered on the Saudi Stock Exchange. To achieve the goal of the study, content analysis was used for Factors affecting the level of accounting disclosure on sustainable development practices and its relationship to the quality of accounting profits by examining and analyzing the annual reports of a sample of 143 companies registered in the Saudi Stock Exchange in the period from 2012 to 2014, and the study found that the level of accounting disclosure about sustainable development practices of the Saudi companies under study has decreased. A positive relationship between the level of disclosure and each of the company's size, profitability, research and development expenditures, the size of the board of directors, the independence of members and the quality of the audit committees. The study also found a positive impact of the accounting disclosure on sustainable development practices on the quality of accounting profits.

The theoretical framework includes:

The concept of accounting disclosure and sustainable development and the relationship between them (GRI Framework)

The definitions of disclosure varied, including what is relevant to it in the financial reports on the one hand that it is a presentation of information to investors in a way that allows predicting the capabilities of the project to achieve profits and thus the ability to pay obligations. Hendrickson defines disclosure as "informing users of financial reports with everything that helps them make their rational economic decisions, whether investment

decisions. Or granting loans or relating to determining the tax burden for each of the joint-stock companies (Hendriksen, 1992: 50) (

Choi (1972: 160) linked the degree of disclosure to reducing the uncertainty of the beneficiaries by publishing economic information related to the project, whether it is quantitative or qualitative information that helps the investor to make his decisions and reduce his uncertainty about economic events. Future. " Disclosure can be dealt with by studying its relationship to communication theory in accounting, as it is a procedure through which the economic unit is connected to the outside world, and the final outcome of those procedures is in the balance sheet, the cash flow statement, and the income statement.

The fifth standard of international accounting standards stipulated the information that should be disclosed, namely:

Information that must be disclosed in the issued financial reports, including the balance sheet, cash flow statement, income statement and notes

Financial information that helps in carrying out studies and launching financial decisions. Clarity of information and making it understandable to achieve safety is required here.

Investor decisions It is well known that the financial reports contain rules imposed by international standards.

Be that as it may, there is an absence of uniform obligation to the terms and approaches of monetary announcing, which contrast starting with one action then onto the next, to accomplish lucidity of the revelation cycle, and prior to explaining the connection among divulgence and manageable turn of events, the idea of practical turn of events:

It implies advancement that requires freedom of chances in areas with the point of harmony between financial development and the establishments of supportable improvement through reasonable administration of assets, reasonable dispersion and limiting the impacts coming about because of the cycle of monetary development, which is to guarantee that the all out load of resources, regardless of whether man-made or characteristic resources acquired (the mountain2019)

Also, manageable advancement from a bookkeeping viewpoint implies corporate manageability as it is a business technique that looks to utilize the best strategic policies to accomplish a harmony between the necessities of current and expected partners. Appropriately, the corporate supportability execution gauges the degree to which organizations consolidate financial, natural and social elements inside their activities and consequently their effect on the venture and society. . (Fred, 2016: 13)

The GRI structure has acquired prominence as a supportability report and acquired help and acknowledgment in the European Union, the United Nations, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development and the World Economic Forum. The primary adaptation of it was delivered in 2000 with the help of the United Nations Development Program in participation with the Consortium of Environmentally Responsible Economists to give an overall structure to the arrangement of maintainability provides details regarding The rules center around straightforwardness and responsibility for ecological, financial and social effects important to an assorted gathering of partners. In 2002, the second form G2 was given, and in 2006 the third release G3, which expected to make revelation more straightforward, and in 2011 the third release was once again introduced and covered extra direction on angles identified with the local area, common liberties and sex equity, and in May 2013 the fourth version was given G4, which gave organizations a two-year cutoff time to change over to execute the fourth form, which has become adherence to in the reports from the finish of 2015.

The point of giving the fourth release was to assist organizations with getting ready target manageability reports that remember helpful and important data for maintainability issues and make supportability reports a standard practice notwithstanding giving direction on the best way to introduce supportability revelations. (Qandil, 2016)

Types, constituents and techniques for bookkeeping divulgence and the components influencing it

There are numerous kinds of bookkeeping revelation, including:

First: full or far reaching divulgence:

It is proposed to focus on the extensiveness of the reports and their inclusion of the data that has an effect. Consequently, the emphasis is on the significance of total honesty of the significance of the budget summaries, which is a fundamental source on which to depend for dynamic.

The verifiable record of the budget summaries substantially influences the recipients of those assertions.

Second: Fair Disclosure:

It alludes to the divulgence worried about the fair consideration of the monetary necessities of the gatherings, as the fiscal summaries and reports ought to be created in a way that accomplishes the non-weighting of the interest of a gathering over a gathering and consequently considering those interests in a reasonable way.

Third: Adequate Disclosure:

What is implied is the presence of the base required bookkeeping data in the budget summaries. Be that as it may, the idea of least is viewed as loose, yet it contrasts as per the necessary requirements and interests as it straightforwardly influences the dynamic.

Fourth: Appropriate Disclosure:

It is a divulgence that fits and suits the prerequisites of information clients and the nature and states of the organization and its action. It isn't simply imperative to uncover the monetary information, yet that it is as essential to speculators and leasers with respect to the action, nature and conditions

Fifth: instructive (media) exposure

The exposure helps in deciding, for example, the revelation of monetary conjectures, and it would decrease the retreat to inward sources to get data casually.

Sixth: Protective Disclosure:

Its point is to give non-deluding revelation to partners and consequently ensure the speculator by giving sound and target data that is coordinated with reasonable exposure to help the unfamiliar financial specialist. (Abdo, 2019)

Intentions in corporate exposure application:

A few scientists accept that there are exceptional thought processes in foundations that cause contamination to the climate, particularly if the foundation's protections and the organization are recorded on the stock trade: (Al-Tahter, 2011)

On account of the positive effect of the divulgence cycle on the normal market estimation of the office by estimating its offer cost on the stock trade

An endeavor to viably react to the pressing factors and needs of true controllers, including the American Stock Exchange Trading Commission (SEC)

The normal accessibility of unique principles that direct the bookkeeping divulgence of the foundations' ecological exhibition. From the abovementioned, it is obvious to us that ecological divulgence ought to be obligatory, particularly in foundations that adversely affect the climate.

Monetary revealing quality norms, pertinence and fundamental goals.

Norms are characterized as rules for estimating cycles and occasions that influence business results and monetary position and hence are a guide for getting ready and introducing monetary qualities. It is realized that the substance and premise of monetary bookkeeping incorporates a few suspicions, rules and standards, which are GAAP acknowledged bookkeeping standards. (Al-Mousawi, 2015)

Bookkeeping writing and examination have underlined the significance of the data contained in the monetary reports and explanations as they are the fundamental sources that are depended upon in settling on venture choices by giving excellent data portrayed by advancement and accommodation, and there is a job for divulgence in expanding the quality and substance of bookkeeping reports as the revelation attempts to guarantee Transparency in budget summaries through complete honesty and by reasonable introduction of valuable and vital data for dynamic to a wide scope of clients. With respect to straightforwardness, it implies giving data and information identified with its exercises and setting them at the removal of investors, investors and vendors on the lookout, and not hiding data, as the bookkeeping exposure accomplishes straightforwardness that prompts The nature of the data contained in the fiscal reports to ensure the interests of investors and different gatherings. Each organization is lawfully committed to give fundamental, legitimate data to all vendors.

The divulgence likewise attempts to accomplish the component of importance and validity, so the bookkeeping data appeared in the monetary reports is good for its clients in settling on venture choices, and the similarity is additionally accomplished through the capacity of the client of the bookkeeping data to comprehend the substance of the budget summaries.

Believability communicates the chance of depending on bookkeeping data and confiding in it since it is sensible and liberated from mistakes and inclination, and that it steadfastly presents the financial occasions that it addresses, and all together for the data to gain the trait of validity, it should be portrayed by genuineness of articulation, that is, the substance or the substance and not simply the structure, and with the end goal for believability to be accomplished, the data should be based. Bookkeeping depends on target estimation decides that work through undeniable ideas, and in this manner it should be liberated from mistakes and fair-mindedness in portraying or estimating monetary and financial occasions, and it should be sincerely and really communicated about those occasions, and it is additionally important to depend on worthy guidelines overseeing systems. Confirmation and consistency in application, notwithstanding that, to be decided on the legitimacy of bookkeeping data, time and spatial examinations are made among expenses and benefits or between real outcomes, or what is known as likeness. (Abdo, 2019: 677)

Bookkeeping revelation and its relationship to the nature of reports

The connection between the revelation of practical turn of events and the nature of the monetary report is dependent upon two perspectives. By dissecting the connection between business morals and the nature of the monetary report, it was discovered that organizations that have a more significant level of moral responsibility have less impetuses to rehearse benefit the board and are more traditionalist in the announced benefits and more precise in guaging Future incomes and accordingly moral responsibility is connected to a higher caliber of

monetary detailing, as it is identified with feasible improvement rehearses, and from us, a positive relationship between's revelation of economical turn of events and the nature of the monetary report is normal.

Sustainable development and financial report quality.

Socially responsible companies tend to manage profit to the least extent possible, and managers have moral motives to work, and social responsibility increases the transparency of reports and conceals losses, and disclosure of social and environmental performance improves the performance of partners in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as indicated by a study (Ahmed, 2016). That the disclosure of social responsibility in light of adopting good governance practices leads to an increase in the value of Egyptian companies.

According to the need to create demand for companies, managers are motivated to provide high-quality financial information to meet users' needs and avoid any negative effects of profit management, and the quality of the financial report positively affects the trend towards disclosure, so companies that have high-quality financial information have incentives to provide more information on the social responsibility.

In this context and that there is an integral relationship between the quality of profits as an indicator of the quality of the financial report and the optional financial disclosure, and the disclosure of sustainable development information reduces the asymmetry of information, as companies with lower profit quality have less incentives for optional disclosure and thus investors will look at them less credibly, meaning The disclosure of the sustainability report contributes to improving the quality of accounting information, and therefore there is a positive relationship between the disclosure of sustainable development and the quality of the financial report. (Arafa, 2016)

The relationship between achieving sustainable development disclosure and company value. The sustainability report consists of disclosing the continuous performance of the institution and the concept of triple reports (sustainable development) is summarized by the fact that when evaluating institutions, financial performance is no longer the only determinant of the company's position in the market or the level of the company's success, and companies must respond to the demands of providing more information on the social and environmental impacts It must be taken into account that the three dimensions of sustainable development are considered as one unit, as any element that contributes to the same extent to achieving the ultimate goal of the company, from the economic point of view tripartite reports on the results of the company's business ensure the availability of transparency and timely financial information for investors, workers, customers, partners and suppliers, and from the social point of view this The type of reports is of public interest to the societies in which companies operate and what is related to the environment means the company's protection of resources, product safety, production standards and charters. (Sweet and Long, 2018)

The relationship between accounting disclosure and the quality of investment decisions. The accounting system has a very important role in terms of helping different departments to deliver the necessary information for policy-making and decision-making, as when a certain decision is made, all results are studied and the most important factors that affect the decision-making process are the cost of production and the quality of service provided by the facility and the accountant's task In identifying and counting all costs associated with the activity or production, including environmental costs, which gives a clear and comprehensive picture of activity and production, which leads to improving the quality of accounting information.

It is worth noting that there is a reciprocal relationship between environmental costs and the decision-making process in the facility, as it is assumed that a database of environmental accounting developed by the establishments is used and the environmental costs affect administrative and environmental measures, as well as the correct measurement of the investment value works to improve performance effectiveness and build rational decisions Through the application of the cost return indicator, this gives a clear view of the users of accounting information. It also works to rationalize resource use decisions and thus achieve the reduction of waste that increases the technical and economic efficiency of the facility.

From the above, we agree on the importance of studying the impact of environmental costs in making investment decisions due to the correlation of environmental costs with improving the cost system as a whole and to give a clearer picture of the institution's obligations. Accordingly, the facilities management is required to develop its accounting systems to match the data required to be taken into account in the accounting system. The Commission for Sustainable Development stated in 1998. On the cases and activities that are dealt with by the environmental accounting system and the factors affecting decision-making D, the establishment associated with economic competition and sound environmental management, and ways to adopt policies and procedures to achieve this in the field of environmental management accounting. (Saleh, 2014)

With reference to the benefits of the company's integrated report, it can be divided according to the recipient of the report. For investors, the information available in the report, especially non-financial information, represents a more comprehensive view about the company and its strategic direction. The report can be considered a source of information for making new investment decisions for investors. There is no doubt that the traditional view of financial statements has not It is the basis on which to make new investment decisions or not, given that the financial statements are historical information and do not reflect the future capacity of the company, and large companies have declared their bankruptcy or have involved manipulation in their financial statements despite

their financial statements being audited by the largest external audit firms. Integrated reports increase the effectiveness of disclosure of information and how the company manages its strategy, the effectiveness of governance and the company's performance in line with the external environment of the company and in a way that contributes to creating value for it in the short and long term. (Abdo, 2019: 662)

Determinants of the disclosure of sustainable development and the benefits and advantages of sustainability reports

The companies' decision to disclose is related to the size of the benefit and the cost of this decision, and the benefits and advantages of sustainability reports are:

First: Sustainability reports help in improving the company's image in society in a way that leads to increased sales, achievement of competitive advantages, and improvement of financial performance as a whole.

Second: To legitimize the company's activities and products and improve its reputation as a responsible company that manages the efficiency of operations on environmental and social issues.

By providing new financial resources that may be less costly to investors interested in social and environmental issues, this helps reduce risks through easy access to lenders.

Fourth: Improving the company's credit rating rate and thus the company's financial success and helping it attract long-term capital

Fifth: Compliance with rules and legislation, and thus increased confidence of government agencies in the company, thus achieving tax savings and reducing legal pressures regarding business rules.

Sixth: Increasing accountability and transparency, and thus improving the company's credibility.

Seventh: Sustainability information is an essential element for analyzing financial performance, as the financial disclosure does not show all the risks and liabilities associated with the company's activity, and sustainability is a strength standard for corporate governance and leads to improving the quality of financial reports.

Eighth: It provides environmental and social indicators that help the company internally and externally, and thus helps corporate governance and resource management. It also provides a framework for financial analysts to understand the interrelation between environmental, social and economic performance, as well as improving employee productivity, increasing their motivation, and reducing future operating costs associated with energy, materials and wasted time. (Qandil, 2016)

Chapter Three: Field Study

Study Approach:

The current study followed the descriptive and analytical approach and the case study approach by applying it to the budgets of Almarai Company for the period from (2010 to 2019). Therefore, methods of measurement, classification and interpretation are used with the aim of extracting significant conclusions, then reaching generalizations about the phenomenon under study. "(Saber and Khafajah, 2002, 87)

Study population:

The study population consisted of Almarai Company's financial reports that were published on the company's official website.

The study sample

The researcher identified a sample of the study in the financial reports of Almarai Company for the period from 2010 to 2019 to represent the study population.

Study tool

After reviewing the literature and previous studies related to the subject of the study, the researcher designed a scale for the accounting disclosure for sustainable development and the quality of financial reports as well as the company value index.

Study procedures:

To abide by the limits of the study, and to answer its questions, follow the next researcher

Many previous studies and research in this field, whether Arab or foreign, have been viewed, and the study tool has been identified, prepared and prepared, which is the measure of accounting disclosure on sustainable development, the quality of reports, and the value of the company. Then, the study tool was presented to specialists in financial analysis and review to ensure its validity and suitability for the study's questions, and then to make the necessary deletion and amendment in light of their proposals. The study tool was applied to an exploratory sample of budgets in order to verify the validity and reliability of the current study tool. The results were monitored, analyzed and interpreted, and recommendations and suggestions made.

Statistical methods

Based on the nature of the research and the goals it sought to achieve, the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program and the results were extracted according to the following statistical methods:

Pearson Correlation Coefficient: To reveal the relationship between the scale dimensions, below are the dimensions of the scale and the data tested.

year	The accounting disclosure of sustainable development		Quality of financial reports		The company value	
2010	Number of employee	17.391	convenience	good	Intangible assets	793
	The environment	Not exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	35.5%
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	1.285.4
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Net invested capital	11047
	Financial Sustainability Report	Not exist	comparability	good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	Not exist				
2011	Number of employee	22000	convenience	good	Intangible assets	821
	The environment		credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	23
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	1.140
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Net invested capital	13805
	Financial Sustainability Report	Not exist	comparability	good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	Not exist				
2012	Number of employee	28000	convenience	good	Intangible assets	1335
	The environment	exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	25.4
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	1.4
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Net invested capital	16829
	Financial Sustainability Report	Not exist	comparability	good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	Not exist				
2013	Number of employee	34000	convenience	good	Intangible assets	1331.510
	The environment	exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	31.5
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	1.502
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Net invested capital	19344
	Financial Sustainability Report	Not exist	comparability	good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	Not exist				
2014	Number of employee	38300	credibility	Very good	Intangible assets	1350
	The environment	exist				
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	The market value of a share	46
	The government report	exist	clarity	Very good	Net profit	1.674
	Financial Sustainability Report	exist	comparability	Very good	Net invested capital	21.041
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				

2015	Number of employee	42000	convenience	Very good	Intangible assets	1.009.071
	The environment	exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	46.9
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	1.916
	The government report	exist	clarity	Very good	Net invested capital	22.586
	Financial Sustainability Report	exist	comparability	Very good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				
	An accounting disclosure report for sustainable development	exist				
2016	Number of employee	44500	convenience	Very good	Intangible assets	930.725
	The environment	exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	54.8
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	2.148
	The government report	exist	clarity	Very good	Net invested capital	4.451
	Financial Sustainability Report	exist	comparability	Very good	Capital investments	
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				
	An accounting disclosure report for sustainable development	exist				
2017	Number of employee	42.664	convenience	Very good	Intangible assets	1.046.607
	The environment	exist	credibility	Very good	The market value of a share	53.750
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	Very good	Net profit	2.182
	The government report	exist	clarity	Very good	Capital investments	2.850
	Financial Sustainability Report	exist	comparability	Very good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				
		exist				
2018	Number of employee	42.971	convenience	Very good	Intangible assets	1.038.371
	The environment	exist	credibility	excellent	The market value of a share	48
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	excellent	Net profit	2.012
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Capital investments	1.959
	Financial Sustainability Report	exist	comparability	Very good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				
	An accounting disclosure report for sustainable development	exist				

2019	Number of employee	42.382	convenience	Very good	Intangible assets	1.128.533
	The environment	exist	credibility	excellent	The market value of a share	49.5
	Societal responsibility	exist	transparency	excellent	Net profit	1.812
	The government report	exist	clarity	good	Capital investments	1.650
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist	comparability	Very good		
	Disclosure and transparency report	exist				
		exist				

By calculating the standards of correlation:

In relation to the quality of financial reports and the value of the company ,Pearson correlation coefficients for environmental disclosure achieved the following:

Standards for company value and quality of financial reports	The environmental report	
The market value of a share	An accounting disclosure report for sustainable developments	0.962
	Moral	0.000
Net profit	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.921
	Moral	0.000
The standard of suitability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.890-
	Moral	0.001
The standard of transparency	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.760-
	Moral	0.022
The standard of comparability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.890
	Moral	0.001

By analyzing the Pearson correlation coefficient between the environmental report as one of the accounting disclosure reports on sustainability, it was found that there was a positive direct correlation with a statistical significance of (0.962) for a significant (0.000) with the value of the market share by calculating the correlation relationship with the net profit it was directly related " with a statistical significance 0.921," for significant (0.000)

So we are sure that there is a relationship between the presence of environmental report as one of dimensions of disclosure reports on sustainable development on the value of the company. And for the standard quality of reports, there is a negative correlation " with statistical significance" with the standard suitability of reports to needs, transparency and comparability Which indicates the presence of a relationship between the accounting disclosure on sustainable development and the value of the company. But , this effect is opposite to the quality of the financial reports, and there is no statistical significance with the standard of credibility and clarity.

Standards for company value and quality of financial reports	Financial Sustainability Report	
The market value of a share	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0,954
	Moral	0.000
Net profit	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.883
	Moral	0.001
The standard of suitability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1

	Moral	0.000
The standard of clarity	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.667
	Moral	0.035
The standard of comparability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1
	Moral	0.000

By analyzing the correlation coefficient of Pearson between the financial sustainability report, the standard of company value and the quality of the financial reports, a negative correlation was found "with a statistical significance of (0.954)" for significant (0.000) with the market value of the share , and a negative relationship of (0.883) for a significant (0.001) with the net profit

So that there is an inverse relationship between the financial sustainability report and the value of the company through the net profit index and the market value of the share. By calculating the correlations: in relation to the quality of the financial reports and the value of the company ,Pearson correlation coefficients for the report on disclosure and transparency achieved the following:

Standards for company value and quality of financial reports	Disclosure and transparency report	
The market value of a share	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0,954
	Moral	0.000
Net profit	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.883
	Moral	0.001
The standard of suitability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1
	Moral	0.000
The standard of clarity	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.667
	Moral	0.035
standard of comparability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	1
	Moral	0.000

Through the correlation between the disclosure and transparency report , the value of the company and the quality of the financial reports, it was found that there is an inverse relationship " with statistical significance" with the market value of the share at a ratio of (0.954) for a significant (0.000) and a net profit of (0.883) for a significant (0.001).

There is a positive relationship "with statistical significance" with the quality standards of financial reports, including the standard of adequacy of (1) for significant (0.000), clarity (0.667) for significant (0.035), and comparability of (1) for significant (0.000).

By calculating the correlation relationships: in relation to the quality of financial reports and the value of the company, Pearson correlation coefficients for the sustainable development disclosure report achieved the following:

Standards for company value and quality of financial reports	Sustainable Development Disclosure Report	
The market value of a share	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0,829
	Moral	0.006
Net profit	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.884
	Moral	0.001
The standard of suitability	Pearson Correlation	0.816

	Coefficient	
	Moral	0.004
The standard of comparability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.816
	Moral	0.004

Through the relationships between the presence of a report on the disclosure of sustainable development with the standards of the value of the company and the quality of the financial reports ,a statistically significant inverse relationship was found with the market share value by (0.829) for significant (0.006) and net profit by (0.884) for significant (0.001). for the standards for the quality of financial reports, there is a positive statistically significant relationship with the suitability stadard of (0.816) for Significant (0.004) and the comparability standard (0.816) for significant (0.004).

Standards for company value and quality of financial reports	Index of the number of human resources as an indicator of the sustainability of human resources	
The market value of a share	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.962
	Moral	0.000
Net profit	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.921
	Moral	0.000
The standard of suitability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.890
	Moral	0.001
The standard of tranparency	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-.706
	Moral	0.022
The standard of comparability	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	-0.890
	Moral	0.001

By reviewing the correlations between the index of the number of human resources, the value of the company and the quality standards of financial reports, there had been positive relationship with statistical significance of (0.962) for significant (0.000) with the market value of the share and net profit of (0.921) for significant (0.000) and there is an inverse relationship with the compatibility standard was (0.890) for significant (0.001), the transparency standard was (0.706) for significant (0.022), and the comparability standard was (0.89) for significant (0.001).

Results:

By analyzing the Pearson correlation coefficient between the environmental report as one of the accounting disclosure reports on sustainability, it found the existence of a positive direct correlation with the market value of the stock and the net profit, and thus we can confirm that there is a relationship between the existence of the environment report as one of the dimensions of the disclosure reports on sustainable development on the value of the company.

As for the standard of reporting quality, there is a negative correlation with statistical significance with the standard of relevance of reports to needs, transparency and comparability, which indicates the existence of a relationship between the accounting disclosure of sustainable development and the value of the company, but this effect is inversely related to the quality of financial reports, and there is no statistical significance with the standard of reliability and clarity.

By analyzing the correlation coefficient of Pearson between the financial sustainability report and the standards of the company's value and the quality of the financial reports, it found a negative correlation with the market value of the stock and the net profit, and thus there is an inverse relationship between the financial sustainability report and the company value through the net profit index and the stock market value.

In terms of the relationship between the financial sustainability report and the quality of the financial reports, I found a positive statistically significant positive relationship with the standard of relevance to the needs of the

report, the criterion of clarity and the criterion of comparability, and there is no statistical significance in terms of the standard of transparency and credibility.

In terms of the relationship of correlation between the disclosure and transparency report and the value of the company and the quality of the financial reports, an inverse relationship with statistical significance was found with the market value of the stock and net profit, and there is a positive relationship with statistical significance with the criteria for the quality of financial reports, including the standard of suitability, clarity and comparability.

Through the correlations between the existence of a report for the disclosure of sustainable development with the standards of the value of the company and the quality of the financial reports, there was found an inverse relationship with statistical significance with the market value of the stock and net profit, and with regard to the standards of quality of financial reports, there is a positive relationship with statistical significance with the standard of suitability and the criterion of comparability.

By reviewing the correlations between the index of the number of human resources, the value of the company and the standards of quality of financial reports, there is a positive relationship with statistical significance with the market value of the stock and net profit, and there is an inverse relationship with the proportionality standard, the transparency standard and the comparability standard.

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